

Project number: 730879

Project acronym: INFRAFRONTIER2020

Project title: Development of mouse mutant resources for functional analyses of human diseases - Enhancing the translation of research into innovation

D5.1 Production of 6 genome-edited rat models

Compiled by:

Asrar Ali Khan, INFRAFRONTIER GmbH

Input from:

Mohammed Selloum, Phenomin-ICS

Tania Sorg, Phenomin-ICS

Jan Rozman, CCP

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 730879.

Table of contents:

- Call Information 3**
- Overview of Applications..... 6**
- Selected Applications 7**
- Outcomes 10**
- Outlook 11**
 - Hidden costs 11
 - User feedback..... 11
 - Stand-alone dedicated INFRAFRONTIER service 11
- Application Form 1 12**
- Application form 2..... 21**

Call Information

Provision of access to the following infrastructure:

INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure

Description of the infrastructure

Name of the infrastructure and its installations:

INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure

The mammalian model development service for rat is provided via the INFRAFRONTIER portal by the following organisations:

- Institute of Molecular Genetics of the ASCR, v.v.i., Czech Centre for Phenogenomics (CCP)
- Centre Européen de Recherche en Biologie et Médecine - Groupement d'Intérêt Economique CERBM-GIE (ICS Mouse Clinical Institute)

Location (town, country) of the infrastructure:

Munich, Germany, is the seat of the INFRAFRONTIER legal entity operating the INFRAFRONTIER portal; IMG, Prague, Czech Republic; CERBM-GIE / ICS, Strasbourg, France.

Web site address: www.infrafrontier.eu

Annual operating costs (excl. investment costs) of the infrastructure (€):

- Institute of Molecular Genetics, Czech Centre for Phenogenomics (CCP): 4.000.000€
- CERBM-GIE (ICS Mouse Clinical Institute): 3.960.293€

Description of the infrastructures:

The infrastructure required for running WP5 was provided by six independent INFRAFRONTIER nodes offering this service routinely to researchers of their institutions, to external clients and / or as partners in large collaborative research projects such as the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium (IMPC). They are equipped with up-to-date tools and have access to animal facilities where genetically modified animals are housed in specific units, their use is registered and reported to authorities and inspections are performed on a regular basis. They have proven capability to produce genetically-modified animals using a variety of approaches such as ES cell injections and have adopted new gene editing technologies such as CRISPR/Cas9. All partners have specialized personnel with the required expertise to produce genetically-modified animals using state-of-art technologies. All production units are associated with the corresponding archiving facilities at each centre. This allows the cryopreservation of all new mouse and rat lines created by the Transnational Access service and ensures access to the wider scientific community.

Access units:

The free-of-charge access units covered 1) production of genetically engineered rat models (knock-out or knock-in using genome editing or homologous recombination in rat ES cells) and 2) production of genetically engineered mouse models (knock-out or knock-in using

genome editing). The work started with project design and ended with the delivery of a minimum of F1 genome-edited mouse or rat models.

Services currently offered by the infrastructures:

The WP5 partners routinely provide mouse model development services using all standard approaches such as gene targeting, the generation of chimeric mice from gene-targeted ES cells and gene editing technologies such as TALENs or CRISPR/Cas9. More recently both the ICS and the IMG applied gene editing technologies to generate rat models. Each of the participating centers engaged in large scale in house or international production projects like the IMPC have a capacity of 100 to 150 model development projects per year (ICS, IMG, GRL). Partners operating transgenic service platforms have a capacity of producing on average 15 mouse models per year (Fleming, CSIC, NKI). Rat model development has been validated at both ICS and IMG and the number of projects in development is rapidly increasing. At present 20 rat model development projects are completed or underway. Services are provided to academic and industry clients from across the world.

CRISPR/Cas9 licensing:

Licensing needs to offer the mammalian model development service as TA were discussed with the Broad Institute who owns IP in the technology. Permission was obtained from Broad to provide the offered service to academic applicants. Licenses are needed for further distribution of produced models by the EMMA repository and discussions on licensing conditions have been initiated.

Description of work

Modality of access under this proposal:

- A total of 28 access units were advertised for WP5 through the public INFRAFRONTIER website (www.infrafrontier.eu) with **6 access units for rat model generation** in 3 calls.
- The conditions for free access were 1) the user must work in an institution of a Member State or Associated State, 20% of access units will be allocated to international users, and 2) the user must be selected by the INFRAFRONTIER Evaluation Committee. The conditions for the Transnational Access will be displayed on the INFRAFRONTIER website. The successful TA applications will be scheduled in the service pipelines at the participating INFRAFRONTIER nodes.
- The access units consisted of a **minimum of 2 F1 genome-edited rats (6)** or mice (22). If required homologous recombination in rat ES cells will be used as alternative. Depending on the objectives of the project, we will use the most appropriate technology to generate the rat models.

By homologous recombination in ES cells (rat), the protocol included:

- The design of a strategy for the modification of the targeted gene
- The construction of the target vector and electroporation in rat ES cells
- The screening of the ES colonies and the confirmation of ES recombinant clones
- The development of chimeric rats
- The establishment of the genetically modified rat line by breeding with the chimeric rats (Germ Line Transmission (GT) of the mutation)

A minimum of 2 genome-edited rat and mouse models with the desired mutation were shipped to the customer's animal facility by specialised couriers according to standard shipment procedures. The customer must have a valid license to breed and analyse genetically modified rats or mice.

- The access to the INFRAFRONTIER resources allocated to this work package were free-of-charge except shipment cost.
- All requested animals were produced in the SPF units of each participating node following FELASA health status recommendations.
- Shipment times: Genome-edited animals were shipped within 12 months after the request has been approved by the INFRAFRONTIER Evaluation Committee.
- All rat and mouse knockout models produced within WP5 will be also cryopreserved and deposited into the EMMA repository for subsequent use by the scientific community.

Support offered under this proposal:

Beyond the TA service provision, users benefited from extensive user support which covered detailed consulting on project design. Gene editing approaches frequently yield a number of mutant alleles which can be provided and cryopreserved (at additional cost) for later use as only selected founder animals will be bred to the F1 generation. Logistic support will be provided by arranging shipments to the applicant's animal facilities. Colony expansion can be provided at additional cost. For long term availability, new animal models were cryopreserved by the participating production centres and deposited into the EMMA repository.

Outreach to new users:

The offered services for Transnational Access were displayed on the public INFRAFRONTIER website at www.infrafrontier.eu and also advertised through INFRAFRONTIER customer mailing lists and public internet discussion groups such as the MGI-list, transgenic-list and the ISTT-list. We took advantage of our large network and extensive national contacts and mailing lists as well as of our collaboration with global networks such as the IMPC and contacts to other BMS Research Infrastructures and their respective contacts and dissemination channels. For the model development service two calls were published. Efforts were also made to find new users by advertising the TA calls to the global user community taking advantage of new TA call modalities to allocate up to 20% of TA units to non-EU applicants.

Review procedure under this proposal:

The TA Evaluation Committee assessed applications for the model development service offered by the WP5 Transnational Access activity. The Committee was a mixed panel consisting of members of the external INFRAFRONTIER Evaluation Committee and experts of the participating infrastructures. Members of the external committee are experts in the field of mouse genetics and animal sciences who support INFRAFRONTIER for many years with evaluations of strain submissions for the EMMA repository and TA applications e.g. for model development and phenotyping services. Evaluation of all service requests received were based on descriptions of proposed projects involving the mammalian models delivered by the service. Evaluation criteria were excellence of proposed projects, and scientific merit. However, whether users previously benefited from this scheme and if users have access to transgenic units in their institutions was also considered.

Overview of Applications

TA call website: <https://www.infrafrontier.eu/precision-mammalian-model-development-rat-models>

Total number of applications: 10

Gender distribution: 80% male; 20% female

Selected Applications

Production centre	Applicant	Gene of interest	Project scope
PHENOMIN-ICS Partner 5	Bernhagen Germany, LMU, Institute for Stroke and Dementia Research, Munich	Mif – Macrophage migration inhibitory factor	Chemokine-like inflammatory cytokine The critical role in neurobiology, cardiobiology and immunology was shown by the applicant and others using mouse models. Aim of the project is to establish a null MIF rat KO as a complementary rodent model. The rat model facilitates better behavioural analyses, easier surgery, and serial blood draws. The new rat model and use may establish if MIF is a therapeutic target after stroke.
CCP Partner 3	Björnsson Iceland, Landspítali University Hospital Reykjavik	Cst3 – related cerebral amyloid angiopathy	Hereditary CST3-related cerebral amyloid angiopathy (HCCAA) is a lethal dominantly inherited disorder that affects Icelandic families (1/10000). It leads to amyloid deposition in the cerebral vasculature, which leads to stroke and dementia and ultimately to death. The disorder caused by a single variant in the CST3 gene (increases risk of amyloid formation of Cystatin C). Mouse models do not show the expected phenotypes as the immune system may be able to clear amyloids. The applicants hypothesize and expect that a rat model may recapitulate the HCCAA disease phenotype of human patients. The newly developed model would then be used to test drugs and dietary strategies such as a ketogenic diet.
PHENOMIN-ICS Partner 5	Galli France, INSERM Center of Psychiatry and Neurosciences, Paris	Vamp7	VAMP7 is a vesicular SNARE and encodes a protein localizing to late endosomes and lysosomes, and is involved in the fusion of transport vesicles to their target membranes. While mouse KO models are available and display phenotypes such as enlarged ventricle, decreased brain weight, thermoregulation defect, increased blood glycerol and anxiety, the mouse models have limitations as the gene is localized on the X-chromosome. In rat the Vamp7 gene is localized on chromosome 12 and therefore the applicants ask for the production of a rat Vamp7 KO model. This will be an important tool to study heterozygous mutants of both sexes. The expression level of Vamp7 is considered as important for the

			phenotypes. What is more, rat models support a more precise biochemical characterisation of the secretome.
PHENOMIN-ICS Partner 5	Bahram France, University of Strasbourg	Srp54	<p>The applicant's group identified a new gene in a first index-case patient suffering from a bona fide SBDS (Shwachman-Bodian-Diamond syndrome): SRP54, Signal Recognition Particle. Like other SDS (Shwachman-Diamond-syndrome) genes, SRP54 is involved in protein synthesis/co-translation, albeit at different cellular checkpoints.</p> <p>The SRP complex has so far remained unaffected by any disease-causing mutations in SDS and more generally in Severe Congenital Neutropenia (SCN). However, despite evidence confirming the pathogenicity of SRP54 mutations, the underlying pathophysiological mechanisms of this disease linked to SRP54 mutations remains to be elucidated. The main question of this project, still unanswered for the majority of ribosomopathies, is how a central ubiquitous cellular function, such as protein biosynthesis/co-translation, can lead to a very narrow and specific phenotype. Key expected results of the projects are to establish a link between mutations in SRP54 and the phenotypic manifestations in patients, and to understand how mutations in SRP54 lead to SDS and neutropenia.</p> <p>The applicant aims to develop a heterozygous SRP54 T117 del knock-in rat model, recapitulating a recurrent in-frame deletion identified in patients. In contrast to the mouse genome which harbors three copies of the SRP54 gene, the rat as well as the human genome carries only one copy.</p>
CCP Partner 3	Trezza Italy, Roma Tre University, Rome	FMR1	<p>FMR1 (fragile X mental retardation 1) gene</p> <p>The main disease related to changes in the FMR1 gene is Fragile X syndrome</p> <p>Other disorders relate to the number of CGG triplets e.g. children with a permutation (55-200 CGG repeats) in the FMR1 gene have learning disabilities, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, intellectual disability, and autism spectrum disorder.</p> <p>Relevance of generating a rat FMR1 mutant line</p>

			<p>Approved therapies for Fragile X syndrome are not yet available and there is an urgent and unmet need to search for treatments able to modify the lifetime course of FXS and to improve symptoms. In this context rat models are excellent tools to understand disease mechanism and to validate new therapeutic targets and drug candidates. Behavioral features displayed by FXS patients such as impaired cognition and altered social behaviors can be better modelled in rats and have thus more translational relevance to the human disease. Furthermore, the larger size of the rat brain makes brain surgery much easier. The applicant is interested in developing a true Fmr1-KO model.</p>
CCP Partner 3	Svoboda Czech Republic, IMG Prague	Dicer	<p>Dicer is the key enzyme in the production of small RNAs guiding sequence-specific repression in microRNA and RNA interference pathways. Dicer supports microRNA biogenesis but does not efficiently support RNAi because it is poorly processing endogenous dsRNA, with the exception of oocytes. They express a variant called Dicer^o which cleaves dsRNA. Dicer^o evolved through insertion of an MT family retrotransposon into intron 6 leaving behind a LTR acting as oocyte specific promoter driving expression of a Dicer variant lacking its N-terminal helicase domain. Dicer^o mRNA dominates Dicer transcripts in mouse and rat oocytes.</p> <p>Research question: Is RNAi important for rat oocytes, and how differs the repertoire of RNAi-controlled genes between mice and rats? The requested rat model will have the LTR promoter controlling expression of Dicer^o removed in rat oocytes. KO animals will be assessed for viability and fertility.</p> <p>The rat model is needed as it is the only currently available model, which can address the issue of evolution of RNAi pathway function and significance.</p>

Outcomes

User	Project (gene)	Design completed	Design approved	Injections or Electroporations Planned/started	Rat pups born	Planned mutations confirmed	Rat F1 shipped to researcher
Bernhagen, Germany	<i>Mif</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Galli, France	<i>Vamp7</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Bahram, France	<i>Srp54</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Björnsson, Iceland	<i>Cst3</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Svoboda, Czech Republic	<i>Dicer</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Trezza, Italy	<i>Fmr1</i>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Postponed due to Covid-19

Outlook

The rat models for Dr. Trezza were planned to be sent to Italy in November/December 2020 but World Courier was not able to safely transport the animals due to the COVID-19 pandemic. CCP decided to house the rats and made new breeding pairs. Dr. Trezza confirmed to pay for the extra costs associated with this additional task. Recently, 3 new litters were obtained, weaned in CW3 2021, genotyped in CW4 and will be sent to Italy in CW8 (22.02.21). However, further difficulties could be possible due to the current pandemic situation.

Hidden costs

There were no significant hidden costs associated with the access units. In one case, the COVID-19 pandemic prevented the transfer of the rats to the user. Additional costs for breeding and generation of new animals was borne by the user.

User feedback

The following feedback was provided by Dr. Galli:

INFRAFRONTIER selected our proposal to generate the VAMP7 KO in rat. The project was conducted swiftly and we are currently characterizing this new line. We would not have been able to obtain this important new animal model without the support of INFRAFRONTIER and the excellent services provided by the Mouse Clinics ICS.

Stand-alone dedicated INFRAFRONTIER service

There was not a lot of initial demand for the rat models. However, an increase in demand for precision rat models is expected to rise with the efficient adaption of CRISPR-Cas9 genome editing technologies for rat model generation.

In a recent survey of TA call providers, WP5 partner Phenomin-ICS have expressed interest in adapting this pilot TA call into an independent sustainable service outside of I2020 and extending it with phenotyping capabilities and non-regulatory preclinical testing. The latter point was backed up by a TA call user requesting additional fee-for-service analysis on the lines that was successfully provided by Phenomin-ICS. The next step is to incorporate the experiences from this pilot service towards achieving this goal.

Application Form 1

INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure

INFRAFRONTIER2020 Project - Trans-national Access call

January 2019

Precision mammalian model development / rat

Call information and application form

Context and aims of the call

INFRAFRONTIER is the European Research Infrastructure for phenotyping and archiving of model mammalian genomes. The INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure provides access to first-class tools and data for biomedical research, and thereby contributes to improving the understanding of gene function in human health and disease using rodent models. The core services of INFRAFRONTIER comprise the systemic phenotyping of mouse mutants in the participating mouse clinics, and the archiving and distribution of mouse mutant lines by the European Mouse Mutant Archive (EMMA).

Main objective of this INFRAFRONTIER open call is to facilitate access for the wider biomedical research community to the unique infrastructure and scientific expertise of the participating INFRAFRONTIER partners, to deliver novel rat mutant models that will advance knowledge of human disease and will be of widespread use in biomedical science. Many cognitive and physiological characteristics that make the rat an ideal human disease model and choice for laboratory studies in neurobiology, cardiobiology, and immunology. Recent advances in genome-editing technology will be used to develop new rat models of human disease. INFRAFRONTIER will provide open access to all newly developed disease models through the European Mouse Mutant Archive (EMMA). Access to this free-of-charge-service will be granted on the basis of the applicant's research plans and the potential impact of the proposed novel rat model on the wider biomedical research community.

This Trans-national Access call of the INFRAFRONTIER2020 project supports a total of 3 precision rat model development projects. A complementary call provides support for 12 customised mouse model development projects.

The INFRAFRONTIER2020 project has received funding from the EU Research and Innovation programme Horizon 2020 (H2020-EU.1.4.1.1. Developing new world class research infrastructures)

Trans-national Access (TA) activity of the INFRAFRONTIER2020 project

Free of charge precision rat model development service / Access modalities

- The EC Horizon 2020 funded INFRAFRONTIER2020 project (2017 – 2020) supports eligible customers with a free-of-charge rat model development service implemented as a Trans-national Access activity supporting a total of 3 projects in this call.
- The **access unit** offered covers the production of a single F1 genome-edited rat line (at least one individual of a F1 genome edited rat line will be provided).
- The **model development service** using **genome editing** involves project design, preparation of sgRNAs and Cas9 mRNA/protein, and injection into zygotes to generate F0 founder mutant animals (Sprague Dawley genetic background). Selected F0 animals (very often mosaic) will be bred to germ line to produce F1 genome edited animals. **Possible allele types that can be generated are indels, exon deletions (< 10kb) and point mutation insertions.**
- Newly developed rat models will be made available to selected applicants within an average of 12 months following provision of all required information to start the rat production.
- The generated **rat models will be made available to the scientific community**. An optional grace period of up to 1 year for rat models may apply, with immediate release of rat resources after expiry of the grace period. Rat mutant lines will be deposited into the INFRAFRONTIER/EMMA repository for subsequent use by the scientific community. Newly developed rat models will be owned by the production centres and will be distributed by the INFRAFRONTIER/EMMA repository using their institutional MTAs.
- **Costs:** The access to the INFRAFRONTIER2020 model development service is free of charge. However, the shipment cost of the newly developed rat models must be borne by the applicants.
- **Eligibility:** The INFRAFRONTIER2020 **Trans-national Access call is open** and proposals can be submitted from applicants around the world. Two projects must be allocated to applicants from EU Member States and Associated Countries, and one project can be allocated to applicants from third countries.
- **Application:** Service requests for the INFRAFRONTIER2020 model development service can be made via this **application form**. Applications for the Trans-national Access activity must include a short description of the research plans for utilising the newly developed rat model that is being generated by the INFRAFRONTIER2020 TA service.
- **Selection procedure:** Proposals from eligible customers for free of charge access to the INFRAFRONTIER2020 rat model development service will be subject to a review procedure. The review will be based on short descriptions of the projects involving the rat mutants that will be produced by the TA service. A mixed panel of members of INFRAFRONTIER and of an external Evaluation Committee will assess service requests supported by the TA activity. In addition to scientific merit of applicants, soundness of the proposal and research plans, and the beneficial impact of the proposed novel rat model on the wider biomedical

research community will be assessed. Applicants will be informed on the outcome of the evaluation within 6 weeks after the end of the call for which the TA application was submitted. All applications will be handled with strict confidentiality.

- **Acknowledgements:** Please do acknowledge any support under this scheme in all resulting publications with "Part of this work has been funded by the European Union Research and Innovation programme Horizon 2020 (Grant Agreement Number 730879). The participating infrastructure which provided the service should be specifically mentioned in any publication resulting from the service.

Support offered

Beyond the TA service provision applicants will benefit from extensive user support which covers detailed consulting on project design. Gene-editing approaches frequently yield a number of mutant alleles which can be provided and cryopreserved (at additional cost) for later use as only selected founder animals will be bred to the F1 generation. Logistic support will be provided by arranging shipments to the applicant's animal facilities. At additional cost a colony expansion can be provided. For long-term availability new animal models will be cryopreserved by the participating production centres at own cost and deposited into the EMMA repository (<https://www.infrafrontier.eu/resources-and-services/deposit-mice-emma-repository>).

The participating INFRAFRONTIER partners routinely provide mouse and rat model development services using all standard approaches such as gene targeting, the generation of chimeric mice from gene-targeted ES cells and gene editing technologies such as TALENs or CRISPR/Cas9. The participating centres are engaged in large-scale mouse production projects like the IMPC and have a capacity of 100 to 150 model development projects per year. Furthermore, model development services are provided to academic and for-profit clients from across the world.

Participating infrastructures:

- Czech Centre for Phenogenomics - <https://www.phenogenomics.cz/>
- PHENOMIN-ICS - <http://www.phenomin.fr/en-us/>

Application Form - INFRAFRONTIER2020 precision rat model development service Closing of call on February 15th - Evaluation process until March 15th

First name	
Family name	

Email	
Phone	
Fax	
Institution	
Address	
Town	
Postcode	
Country	
Link to lab website	
Link to publication list	

**The following data is required by the EC for statistical purposes.
Applications can only be considered if all data are provided.**

Gender	
Birth year	
Nationality	
Researcher status (e.g. Prof, Postdoc)	
Scientific background	

I have read, understood and agree to the [INFRAFRONTIER data privacy policy](#)

Description of proposed project

Please describe briefly the proposed project involving the rat mutant line to be developed using genome editing technology. This description will be the foundation for the evaluation of your project. Informal enquiries prior to proposal submission are welcome via proposals@infrafrontier.eu

Gene of interest	

Please, do not extend beyond the provided space (max 2 pages including references).

Send your proposal to proposals@infrafrontier.eu by February 15th 2019.

[INFRAFRONTIER2020 project description](#)

INFRAFRONTIER2020 - Towards enduring mouse resources and services advancing research into human health and disease

INFRAFRONTIER2020 objectives

The INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure integrates European Mouse Clinics and the European Mouse Mutant Archive (EMMA) with the common goal to ensure access to mouse

models for basic research of human health and disease, and to translate this knowledge into therapeutic approaches for the benefit of the European society.

The expanded INFRAFRONTIER2020 network, coordinated by the INFRAFRONTIER GmbH, includes 3 SMEs and is strategically responding to the INFRADEV3 call with aligned objectives to advance the long-term sustainability which are **1)** development of business models and a stable legal framework; **2)** raise awareness of the INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure; **3)** provide bespoke services aligned with user demands; **4)** promote best practices in mouse phenogenomics; **5)** enhance robustness of the INFRAFRONTIER IT infrastructure and use of the EMMA strain resource; and **6)** improve business processes. Towards achieving these objectives key INFRAFRONTIER2020 project deliverables are:

- INFRAFRONTIER Business Plan2.0, and business models for all services
- Stable legal framework built on the INFRAFRONTIER legal entity
- INFRAFRONTIER annual stakeholder conferences
- Customised mouse model and secondary phenotyping pilot services
- INFRAFRONTIER advanced training schools in mouse phenogenomics
- Reengineered EMMA Database2.0 system
- Annotated mouse models of human diseases
- Quality management system for the legal entity

INFRAFRONTIER2020 will **1)** enhance the sustainable operation of the INFRAFRONTIER RI; **2)** continue to structure the ERA, **3)** foster innovation, and **4)** address major societal challenges in human health by customised service pilots supporting research into common and rare diseases. A sustainable INFRAFRONTIER RI will ensure the quality of deposited mice and support the reproducibility of biological results. Outreach efforts will raise awareness of resources and services and facilitate sustainable engagement with industry and global consortia such as the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium

The INFRAFRONTIER2020 project has received funding from the EU Research and Innovation programme Horizon 2020 (H2020-EU.1.4.1.1. Developing new world class research infrastructures)

Participating INFRAFRONTIER mouse clinics

Czech Centre for Phenogenomics (CCP) / <http://www.phenogenomics.cz/>

The Czech Centre for Phenogenomics provides expertise and services to the biomedical research community which study the function of genes in biological processes and / or human disorders in vivo using mouse or rat models. CCP covers a full spectrum of genetic engineering services, strain cryopreservation and archiving services, advanced phenotyping and imaging services, as well as specific pathogen free (SPF) animal housing and husbandry.

Phenomin-ICS / <http://www.phenomin.fr/>

PHENOMIN is founded by 3 major national nodes: the Institut Clinique de la Souris (ICS, Illkirch), the Transgenesis and Archiving of Animal Models (TAAM, Orléans, Villejuif) and the Centre for Immunophenomics (CIPHE, Marseille) that are devoted to serve the scientific community for the usage of mouse models. PHENOMIN constitutes a unique distributed resource for the creation, the care, the phenotyping, the distribution and archiving of animal models for academics and private corporations.

The **ICS** is a large-scale facility open to the community that ensures the generation of mouse models à la carte, the validation of genetic models, the expansion and preservation and distribution of models with the housing department, and offers in its phenotyping department a series of standardized functional analysis of mouse models that can be performed in a comprehensive pipeline or on demand, as well as for more specialized studies, that cover the major functions and key physiological systems.

Application form 2

INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure

INFRAFRONTIER2020 Project - Trans-national Access call

May 2019

Precision mammalian model development / rat

Call information and application form

Context and aims of the call

INFRAFRONTIER is the European Research Infrastructure for phenotyping and archiving of model mammalian genomes. The INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure provides access to first-class tools and data for biomedical research, and thereby contributes to improving the understanding of gene function in human health and disease using rodent models. The core services of INFRAFRONTIER comprise the systemic phenotyping of mouse mutants in the participating mouse clinics, and the archiving and distribution of mouse mutant lines by the European Mouse Mutant Archive (EMMA).

Main objective of this INFRAFRONTIER open call is to facilitate access for the wider biomedical research community to the unique infrastructure and scientific expertise of the participating INFRAFRONTIER partners, to deliver novel rat mutant models that will advance knowledge of human disease and will be of widespread use in biomedical science. Many cognitive and physiological characteristics that make the rat an ideal human disease model and choice for laboratory studies in neurobiology, cardiobiology, and immunology. Recent advances in genome-editing technology will be used to develop new rat models of human disease. INFRAFRONTIER will provide open access to all newly developed disease models through the European Mouse Mutant Archive (EMMA). Access to this free-of-charge-service will be granted on the basis of the applicant's research plans and the potential impact of the proposed novel rat model on the wider biomedical research community.

This Trans-national Access call of the INFRAFRONTIER2020 project supports a total of 3 precision rat model development projects.

The INFRAFRONTIER2020 project has received funding from the EU Research and Innovation programme Horizon 2020 (H2020-EU.1.4.1.1. Developing new world class research infrastructures)

Trans-national Access (TA) activity of the INFRAFRONTIER2020 project
Free of charge precision rat model development service / Access modalities

- The EC Horizon 2020 funded INFRAFRONTIER2020 project (2017 – 2020) supports eligible customers with a free-of-charge rat model development service implemented as a Trans-national Access activity supporting a total of 3 projects in this call.
- The **access unit** offered covers the production of a single F1 genome-edited rat line (at least one individual of a F1 genome edited rat line will be provided).
- The **model development service** using **genome editing** involves project design, preparation of sgRNAs and Cas9 mRNA/protein, and injection into zygotes to generate F0 founder mutant animals (Sprague Dawley genetic background). Selected F0 animals (very often mosaic) will be bred to germ line to produce F1 genome edited animals. **Possible allele types that can be generated are indels, exon deletions (< 10kb) and point mutation insertions.**
- Newly developed rat models will be made available to selected applicants within an average of 12 months following provision of all required information to start the rat production.
- The generated **rat models will be made available to the scientific community.** An optional grace period of up to 1 year for rat models may apply, with immediate release of rat resources after expiry of the grace period. Rat mutant lines will be deposited into the INFRAFRONTIER/EMMA repository for subsequent use by the scientific community. Newly developed rat models will be owned by the production centres and will be distributed by the INFRAFRONTIER/EMMA repository using their institutional MTAs.
- **Costs:** The access to the INFRAFRONTIER2020 model development service is free of charge. However, the shipment cost of the newly developed rat models must be borne by the applicants.
- **Eligibility:** The INFRAFRONTIER2020 **Trans-national Access call is open** and proposals can be submitted from applicants around the world. Two projects must be allocated to applicants from EU Member States and Associated Countries, and one project can be allocated to applicants from third countries.
- **Application:** Service requests for the INFRAFRONTIER2020 model development service can be made via this **application form**. Applications for the Trans-national Access activity must include a short description of the research plans for utilising the newly developed rat model that is being generated by the INFRAFRONTIER2020 TA service.
- **Selection procedure:** Proposals from eligible customers for free of charge access to the INFRAFRONTIER2020 rat model development service will be subject to a review procedure. The review will be based on short descriptions of the projects involving the rat mutants that will be produced by the TA service. A mixed panel of members of INFRAFRONTIER and of an external Evaluation Committee will assess service requests supported by the TA activity. In addition to scientific merit of applicants, soundness of the proposal and research plans, and the beneficial impact of the proposed novel rat model on the wider biomedical research community will be assessed. Applicants will be informed on the outcome of the

evaluation within 4 weeks after the end of the call for which the TA application was submitted. All applications will be handled with strict confidentiality.

- **Acknowledgements:** Please do acknowledge any support under this scheme in all resulting publications with "Part of this work has been funded by the European Union Research and Innovation programme Horizon 2020 (Grant Agreement Number 730879). The participating infrastructure which provided the service should be specifically mentioned in any publication resulting from the service.

Support offered

Beyond the TA service provision applicants will benefit from extensive user support which covers detailed consulting on project design. Gene-editing approaches frequently yield a number of mutant alleles which can be provided and cryopreserved (at additional cost) for later use as only selected founder animals will be bred to the F1 generation. Logistic support will be provided by arranging shipments to the applicant's animal facilities. At additional cost a colony expansion can be provided. For long-term availability new animal models will be cryopreserved by the participating production centres at own cost and deposited into the EMMA repository (<https://www.infrafrontier.eu/resources-and-services/deposit-mice-emma-repository>).

The participating INFRAFRONTIER partner routinely provides mouse and rat model development services using all standard approaches such as gene targeting, the generation of chimeric mice from gene-targeted ES cells and gene editing technologies such as TALENs or CRISPR/Cas9. The participating centre is engaged in large-scale mouse production projects like the IMPC and has a capacity of up to 50 model development projects per year. Furthermore, model development services are provided to academic and for-profit clients from across the world.

Participating infrastructure:

Czech Centre for Phenogenomics (CCP) / <http://www.phenogenomics.cz/>

The Czech Centre for Phenogenomics provides expertise and services to the biomedical research community which study the function of genes in biological processes and / or human disorders in vivo using mouse or rat models. CCP covers a full spectrum of genetic engineering services, strain cryopreservation and archiving services, advanced phenotyping and imaging services, as well as specific pathogen free (SPF) animal housing and husbandry.

**Application Form - INFRAFRONTIER2020 precision rat model development service
Closing of call on May 31st - Evaluation process until June 30th**

First name	
Family name	
Email	

Phone	
Fax	
Institution	
Address	
Town	
Postcode	
Country	
Link to lab website	
Link to publication list	

**The following data is required by the EC for statistical purposes.
Applications can only be considered if all data are provided.**

Gender	
Birth year	
Nationality	
Researcher status (e.g. Prof, Postdoc)	
Scientific background	

I have read, understood and agree to the [INFRAFRONTIER data privacy policy](#)

Description of proposed project

Please describe briefly the proposed project involving the rat mutant line to be developed using genome editing technology. This description will be the foundation for the evaluation of your project. Informal enquiries prior to proposal submission are welcome via proposals@infrafrontier.eu

Gene of interest	

Please, do not extend beyond the provided space (max 2 pages including references).

Send your proposal to proposals@infrafrontier.eu by May 31st 2019.

[INFRAFRONTIER2020 project description](#)

INFRAFRONTIER2020 - Towards enduring mouse resources and services advancing research into human health and disease

INFRAFRONTIER2020 objectives

The INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure integrates European Mouse Clinics and the European Mouse Mutant Archive (EMMA) with the common goal to ensure access to mouse models for basic research of human health and disease, and to translate this knowledge into

therapeutic approaches for the benefit of the European society.

The expanded INFRAFRONTIER2020 network, coordinated by the INFRAFRONTIER GmbH, includes 3 SMEs and is strategically responding to the INFRADEV3 call with aligned objectives to advance the long-term sustainability which are **1)** development of business models and a stable legal framework; **2)** raise awareness of the INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure; **3)** provide bespoke services aligned with user demands; **4)** promote best practices in mouse phenogenomics; **5)** enhance robustness of the INFRAFRONTIER IT infrastructure and use of the EMMA strain resource; and **6)** improve business processes. Towards achieving these objectives key INFRAFRONTIER2020 project deliverables are:

- INFRAFRONTIER Business Plan2.0, and business models for all services
- Stable legal framework built on the INFRAFRONTIER legal entity
- INFRAFRONTIER annual stakeholder conferences
- Customised mouse model and secondary phenotyping pilot services
- INFRAFRONTIER advanced training schools in mouse phenogenomics
- Reengineered EMMA Database2.0 system
- Annotated mouse models of human diseases
- Quality management system for the legal entity

INFRAFRONTIER2020 will **1)** enhance the sustainable operation of the INFRAFRONTIER RI; **2)** continue to structure the ERA, **3)** foster innovation, and **4)** address major societal challenges in human health by customised service pilots supporting research into common and rare diseases. A sustainable INFRAFRONTIER RI will ensure the quality of deposited mice and support the reproducibility of biological results. Outreach efforts will raise awareness of resources and services and facilitate sustainable engagement with industry and global consortia such as the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium

The INFRAFRONTIER2020 project has received funding from the EU Research and Innovation programme Horizon 2020 (H2020-EU.1.4.1.1. Developing new world class research infrastructures)
